

MUNICIPAL EMERGENCY RESPONSE SYSTEM (MERS) USING GMAPS AND SMS

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ABSTRACT

Municipal Emergency Response System is a complete solution designed to enable effective operations of all emergency response-related activities. It is a rationally developed plan and organizational methodology for responding to and managing emergencies, disasters, and critical situations. It is designed to enable first responders to react more correctly and quickly in a crisis. The system was designed and programmed to handle emergency response issues within the municipality. The integrated emergency management technology utilized SMS (Short Messaging Services) and GMAPS (Google Maps). SMS was used to send brief messages to mobile phones, while Google Maps provided a satellite view of Earth's geographical data suited for emergency response. The system was developed using Agile Software Development, containing 6 phases, from requirements analysis to the tracking and monitoring of the system developed. The evaluation focuses on functionality, efficiency, reliability, and security, aiming to enhance overall emergency response capabilities in the municipality using the ISO 25010 evaluation form from the University. The researchers determined that the system is robust, efficient, user-friendly, reliable, and secure, meeting the needs of emergency responders and contributing to effective emergency response in the municipality.

Keywords: *Agile Software Development, GMAPS, Mobile Phones, Robust, SMS*

INTRODUCTION

The Municipal Emergency Response System (MERS) integrates GMAPS and SMS to create a web-based platform that effectively regulates and manages emergencies using internet connectivity. This system offers user-friendly interfaces for residents, responders, and administrators, which improves coordination and facilitates emergency reporting. By utilizing GMAPS, MERS can generate maps of specific locations, while SMS is used to transmit incident reports and notifications. MERS encompasses emergency response services, communication infrastructure, and emergency management organizations.

Using data collected from seismic events and emergency response operations, the study investigates the correlation between pre-disaster preparedness efforts and post-disaster fatalities. Urban areas that are well-prepared may experience mortality rates of 1% or less, while unprepared areas could see rates exceeding 10% during severe earthquakes (Adams & Martinez, 2023). Additionally, the study explores the utilization of remote sensing and GIS technology to evaluate flood risk in vulnerable areas. It suggests that in well-prepared communities, mortality rates could remain below 5%, whereas in underprepared areas, rates might exceed 20% during catastrophic flooding events (Wong & Ali, 2022). Lastly, the study assesses the impact of typhoon preparedness measures on reducing the death toll in the Philippines. By synthesizing typhoon data and disaster response operations occurrences, the study tests how preparedness-related activities before the catastrophe were associated with the number of fatalities in its aftermath. Specifically, despite the disaster's severity, some high-prepared typhoons keep their fatality rates under 1%, whereas low-prepared areas may suffer rates higher than 5% – and sometimes much larger (Santos & Cruz, 2023). Thus, this test asks to what extent coastal towns in the Philippines are predisposed to storm surge perils. The possession of geography-based software, or GIS software, shows that community preparedness can be affected in the aftermath of a storm surge (Hernandez & Reyes, 2022). The Southern Leyte's vulnerability to disasters such as typhoons, landslides, and earthquakes was evaluated. The mean case fatality rate was between 2% and 10%, but it went as high as 20% in localities with inadequate evacuation centers and homes. In some hilly areas with steep slopes and areas with no forests, landslides killed about 5% to 20% of the people involved. Earthquake deaths were minimal with a case fatality rate of under 5% due to regular seismic retrofitting and public education programs (Cruz & Santos, 2023).

The emergency response to any scenario has been delayed due to worries that the report is insufficient, that information being given to specific responders is delayed, that it is difficult to locate the accident/incident, and that some reports are inaccurate. This study is a demand-pull, which means it is highly relevant and timely in today's condition, as the municipality does not have an automated system for emergency response. To address these concerns, the researchers developed a system for the municipal emergency response team that uses Google Maps to immediately pinpoint accident locations and SMS to report, receive, and announce the full facts and status of the accident, resulting in a more dependable emergency response. This system aims to prevent emergency-related deaths, property damage, and other negative outcomes.

Research Objectives

The researchers aimed to achieve the following objectives;

1. Identify problems faced in the existing process of responding to emergencies in Padre Burgos, Southern Leyte;
2. Design and develop a Municipal Response System (MERS) with GMAPS and SMS;
3. Evaluate the developed system in terms of;
 - 3.1 Functionality,
 - 3.2 Efficiency,
 - 3.3 Reliability, and
 - 3.4 Security.

Conceptual Framework of the Study

Figure 1. This conceptual framework appears to depict a process or system for handling emergency SMS (Short Message Service) alerts or notifications. It consists of three main components: Input, Process, and Output. This system allows users or residents to report emergencies via SMS, processes the incoming messages, extracts relevant information, identifies the location, categorizes the emergency, and generates notifications and maps to assist authorities in responding to the reported emergency.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

METHODOLOGY

According to Dikert et al. (2023), one of the primary advantages of Agile software development in IT is its capacity to adapt to changing requirements and market situations, which is critical in today's fast-changing technological world. Agile processes also promote a culture of transparency, continuous learning, and customer-centric approaches, resulting in higher software quality, faster time-to-market, and better alignment with user needs. The admin can easily manage and use the system, especially if residents send reports/incidents via SMS because it will notify and display each report/incident on the dashboard, and the admin can verify whether the reports are legitimate or not because the residents' contact information should be saved in the

database and displayed on the screen. The materials used in this study are Android smartphones for sending reports/incidents and laptops for managing the system. The study was implemented as pilot testing at Barangay Bunga, which is located in the Municipality of Padre Burgos, Southern Leyte. The researchers randomly selected one administrator, nine responders, and ten Barangay residents. A total of 20 respondents responded to the questionnaire. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale. The study used an adapted evaluation form from the information and descriptive system ISO 25010. The data collected from respondents was analyzed, interpreted, and treated with the Weighted Mean statistical tool.

Figure 2. Agile software development is an iterative and incremental approach in which software is built and delivered in small, repeatable cycles known as iterations. Each iteration consists of a series of operations that are repeated until the finished output is delivered. Step 1. Requirements. During this phase, the requirements for the software product are gathered and defined, including an understanding of end-user's perspective. Step 2. Plan. During this phase, the researchers develop a plan for the next iteration or sprint, breaking the requirements into achievable tasks and estimating the required effort. Step 3. Design. During the design phase, the researchers creates the solution architecture, user interfaces, and other technical components of the software based on the specifications. Step 4. Develop. This phase covers the actual coding and implementation of software functionality by the design standards. Step 5. Release. After development is completed, the software is tested, integrated, and ready for release or deployment in the pilot at barangay Bunga in the municipality of Padre Burgos. Step 6. Track and monitor. This phase entails tracking the performance of the developed system, receiving end-user's input, and determining areas for improvement or new features for the next version.

Figure 2: Agile Software Development

Figure 3. The architectural layout displays a system for secure data processing and storage, with an emphasis on authentication, encryption, and access control measures. At the heart of the architecture is a cloud hosting service that acts as the primary platform for data processing and storage. The system accepts a variety of input sources, including mobile devices, laptops, and desktop computers, and can deliver data securely via encrypted channels. The input data is authenticated, and user credentials are validated to ensure allowed access. This authentication procedure is likely to include components such as an identity management system and security gateways.

Once validated, the data is processed through several phases, including parsing, filtering, and encryption. The encryption component is critical to maintaining the confidentiality and integrity of data during transmission and storage.

The processed data is subsequently saved in a secure database repository, which could be in the cloud or on-premises. Access to this repository is strictly regulated, with only approved persons or systems allowed the required privileges. The system also includes auditing and monitoring capabilities to track and document activities, which ensure accountability and adherence to security laws and regulations. The output from the system can be accessed by authorized users or systems through secure channels, such as encrypted connections or virtual private networks (VPNs). The output may include reports, analytics, or processed data, depending on the specific use case and requirements. Overall, this architectural layout emphasizes the importance of security, data integrity, and access control in a data processing and storage system. It incorporates various security measures, including encryption, authentication, auditing, and access control mechanisms, to protect sensitive data and ensure compliance with security standards and regulations.

Figure 3: Architectural Layout

Figure 4. This diagram represents a use case for a Municipal Emergency Response System (MERS) that utilizes Google Maps (GMaps) and SMS (Short Message Service) technologies. It illustrates the interactions between three main actors: Admin, Responder, and Resident, and the system's functionalities during an emergency situation. Admin: Manage User Account: The admin has the ability to manage user accounts, likely for responders or authorized personnel involved in the emergency response process.

Manage Emergency Data: The admin can manage and maintain data related to emergencies, such as incident reports, resource allocation, or other relevant information. Generate Report: The admin can generate reports based on the emergency data, which could include incident summaries, resource utilization, or other analytical information. Responder: Receive Emergency Notification: The responder receives notifications or alerts about emergency situations, which could be triggered by residents or automated systems. View Emergency Details: The responder can view the details of the reported emergency, including location, severity, and other relevant information. Dispatch Resources: Based on the emergency details, the responder can dispatch appropriate resources, such as emergency services, personnel, or equipment, to the affected area. Resident: Report Emergency: Residents can report emergencies to the system, likely through SMS or other communication channels integrated with the system. View Emergency Updates: Residents can view updates or status information regarding the reported emergency, keeping them informed about the response efforts. Receive Emergency Notification: The system may also send notifications or updates to residents in the affected area, alerting them about the emergency situation and providing instructions or guidance. It highlights the roles and responsibilities of the different actors involved and the flow of information and actions necessary for coordinating emergency response efforts efficiently. By integrating technologies like GMAPS and SMS, the system can leverage location-based data and mobile communication channels to improve situational awareness, resource allocation, and overall emergency management capabilities within a municipal or local government context.

Figure 4: Use Case Diagram

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problems of Existing Manual Process of Emergency Response

Table 1. Problems of Existing Manual Process of Emergency Response

PROBLEMS	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. The manual system could not accurately document the accidents/incidents.	7	10	2	1	0	4.15	Mostly Agree
2. The current manual reporting process is time-consuming.	12	7	1	0	0	4.5	Strongly Agree
3. There is no standardized format for manual accident reporting.	7	11	1	1	0	4.2	Mostly Agree
4. The manual reporting process doesn't have a spot map where the incidents/accidents occurred.	15	4	1	0	0	4.7	Strongly Agree
5. The current process for manually documenting information from phone calls is not efficient.	8	8	3	1	0	4.15	Mostly Agree
6. The manual call reporting is not quick enough to respond to accidents/incidents.	8	10	2	0	0	4.3	Strongly Agree
Average						4.33	Strongly Agree

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Strongly Agree 4.20-3.21 Mostly Agree 3.20-2.61 Agree 2.60-1.81 Slightly Agree 1.80-1.0 Disagree

Table 1. The data gives respondents' (N=20) evaluations on several issues with a manual accident/incident reporting system. The lack of a spot map for incidents/accidents in the manual reporting process (weighted mean = 4.7) is a constraint emphasized by Wang and Chen (2024) in their systematic review, which recognized the lack of spatial data as a significant obstacle to successful event analysis. The manual reporting method is time-consuming (weighted mean = 4.5), which supports Lee and Kim's (2021) suggestion that incident reporting should be automated to improve efficiency and save time spent on manual documentation. The overall "Strongly Agree" interpretation (weighted average = 4.33) suggests that respondents strongly agree with the manual reporting system's difficulties and limitations. This finding emphasized the importance of more efficient, standardized, and automated incident reporting methods to overcome the limitations of manual systems.

Design and Features of the Newly Developed System

Table 2. Design and Features of the Newly Developed System

PROBLEMS	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. Verification for newly registered accounts.	11	8	1	0	0	4.5	Strongly Agree
2. Sending reports, announcements, and feedback in registration are integrated with SMS.	10	9	1	0	0	4.45	Strongly Agree
3. Google Maps to provide accurate location data, allowing emergency services instantly when an incident is reported.	14	6	0	0	0	4.7	Strongly Agree
4. Provide images for proof of the incidents.	13	5	2	0	0	4.55	Strongly Agree
5. Can register a great number of residents or accounts at the same time using bulk registration.	12	7	1	0	0	4.55	Strongly Agree
Average						4.55	Strongly Agree

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Strongly Agree 4.20-3.21 Mostly Agree 3.20-2.61 Agree 2.60-1.81 Slightly Agree 1.80-1.0 Disagree

Table 2. The data contains ratings from respondents (N=20) on the aspects of the newly designed system. Google Maps will provide accurate location data, allowing emergency services to respond immediately when an incident is reported (weighted mean

= 4.7, "Strongly Agree"): The importance of accurate location data and integration with emergency services is consistent with Zhang, Li, and Chen's (2023) claims, which highlighted the critical role of geospatial data and location-based services in emergency response and incident management. Provide images as proof of incidents (weighted mean = 4.55, "Strongly Agree"): The use of visual evidence, such as images, for incident reporting is consistent with Chen & Lee's (2020) recommendations, which emphasized the importance of multimedia data in improving the accuracy and credibility of incident reports. Can register a large number of residents or accounts at once using bulk registration (weighted mean = 4.55, "Strongly Agree"): Kim and Park's (2022) findings support the need for efficient bulk registration processes, identifying the ability to manage large-scale user registration as a critical requirement for scalable and user-friendly digital systems. The total weighted mean of 4.55 and the "Strongly Agree" interpretation indicate that respondents strongly agree on the importance and necessity of the above-mentioned traits or aspects.

Figure 5. The design interface of the Municipal Emergency Response System using GMAPS and SMS. This figure consists of Registration, Administrator, Rescuers, and Residents Login Interfaces.

Figure 5: Login Interface

Figure 6. This is the interface of Sending reports, announcements, and feedback in registration integrated with SMS.

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Figure 6: Sending, Viewing, and Responding of Reports Interface

Figure 7. This is the interface for plotting a spot Map on the location of the reported incidents/accidents using google free open street maps.

Figure 7: Spot Map Interface

Figure 8. This is the main interface of the system which is the dashboard that will display in real-time the Report list, Announcement history, Registered users, and respondded reports.

Figure 8: Main Interface of the System

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Evaluation of the Newly Developed System

Table 3. Functionality of the Newly Developed System

Functionality	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. The system performed the task required.	11	7	1	1	0	4.3	Fully Functional
2. The system provides all of the necessary information to emergency responders	13	6	1	0	0	4.6	Fully Functional
Average						4.45	Fully Functional

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Fully Functional 4.20-3.21 Mostly Functional 3.20-2.61 Functional 2.60-1.81 Slightly Functional 1.80-1.0 Not Functional

Table 3. Based on the given data, which evaluates the functionality of a system. The system performed the task required (weighted mean = 4.3, "Fully Functional"): This finding aligns with the emphasis on task-oriented design and user-centered development principles highlighted by Lee and Kim (2021), who stressed the importance of ensuring that systems effectively fulfill their intended tasks and meet user requirements. The system provides all of the necessary information to emergency responders (weighted mean = 4.6, "Fully Functional"): The provision of comprehensive and relevant information to emergency responders is a critical aspect discussed by Zhang et al. (2023), who examined the role of information systems in enhancing emergency response and incident management. The overall average weighted mean of 4.45 and the "Fully Functional" interpretation suggest that the respondents perceive the system as fully functional in terms of performing the required tasks and providing necessary information to emergency responders.

Table 4. Efficiency of the Newly Developed System

Efficiency	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. The system is efficient in identifying and locating emergencies.	8	8	4	0	0	4.2	Mostly Efficient
2. The system provides efficient real-time updates on the status of emergencies.	13	7	0	0	0	4.65	Very Efficient

3. The responders quickly respond to emergencies using the system.	11	6	2	1	0	4.35	Very Efficient
4. The system is user-friendly and intuitive to operate.	16	3	1	0	0	4.75	Very Efficient
5. The system provides clear and concise instructions for use.	12	7	1	0	0	4.55	Very Efficient
Average						4.5	Very Efficient

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Very Efficient 4.20-3.21 Mostly Efficient 3.20-2.61 Efficient 2.60-1.81 Slightly Efficient 1.80-1.0 Not Efficient

Table 4. Based on the given data, which evaluates the efficiency of a system. The system is easy to use (weighted mean = 4.75, "Very Efficient"): Kim, Park, and Lee (2019) found that user-friendly and intuitive interfaces in emergency management systems have a positive impact on their efficiency and effectiveness. The system provides efficient real-time updates on the status of emergencies (weighted mean = 4.65, "Very Efficient"): Park and Kim (2020) emphasize the importance of real-time data and communication in improving situational awareness and decision-making during emergencies. The overall weighted average of 4.5 and the "Very Efficient" interpretation indicate that respondents believe the system is highly efficient in terms of identifying and locating emergencies, providing real-time updates, enabling quick response, offering user-friendliness and intuitive operation, and providing clear instructions. These findings emphasized the importance of efficient incident detection, real-time data and communication, responsive emergency management, user-friendly interfaces, and clear instructions in the context of emergency management systems.

Table 5. Reliability of the Newly Developed System

Reliability	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. The system is capable of handling errors.	11	7	2	0	0	4.45	Very Reliable
2. The system notifies the user about a wrong data entry.	14	5	1	0	0	4.65	Very Reliable
Average						4.55	Very Reliable

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Very Reliable 4.20-3.21 Mostly Reliable 3.20-2.61 Reliable 2.60-1.81 Slightly Reliable 1.80-1.0 Not Reliable

Table 5. Based on the given data, which evaluates the reliability of a system. With a weighted mean score of 4.45 out of 5, the interpretation is "Very Reliable," implying that respondents thought the system was very capable of handling faults. Mobile application reliability was assessed, as well as error handling and user feedback systems. The authors discovered that good error handling and user alerting tactics considerably increased the perceived reliability of mobile apps. The weighted mean score of 4.65 out of 5 also falls into the "Very Reliable" interpretation range, indicating that respondents found the system to be extremely trustworthy in warning them of incorrect data entries. A comprehensive methodology for assessing the dependability of corporate software systems, including error management, data integrity, and user notifications. Robust error handling and efficient user notification tactics contributed significantly to enhancing enterprise system perceived reliability (Agrawal & Sharma, 2023). The overall weighted mean across both variables is 4.55, indicating "Very Reliable." The researchers investigated similar claims and features of system reliability, error handling, user notifications, and their impact on overall system quality and user experience.

Table 6. Security of the Newly Developed System

Security	RATING (N=20)					Weighted Mean	Interpretation
	5	4	3	2	1		
1. The system ensures the confidentiality of data.	14	5	1	0	0	4.65	Very Secure
2. The system prevents unauthorized access modification to computer programs and/or data.	10	7	3	0	0	4.2	Mostly Secure
3. The system requires the authentication of users.	11	7	2	0	0	4.45	Very Secure
4. A system can generate history logs.	16	3	1	0	0	4.75	Very Secure
Average						4.51	Very Secure

Legend: 5.00-4.21 Very Secure 4.20-3.21 Mostly Secure 3.20-2.61 Secure 2.60-1.81 Slightly Secure 1.80-1.0 Not Secure

Table 6. Based on the given data, which evaluates the security of a system. With a weighted mean score of 4.65 out of 5, the interpretation is "Very Secure," meaning that respondents regarded the system as very secure regarding data confidentiality. Web application security, which includes elements such as data confidentiality, access control, user authentication, and audit logging, has considerably enhanced the system's overall security. (Choi and Kim, 2021). With a weighted mean score of 4.75 out of 5, the interpretation is "Very Secure," with the capacity to generate logs or audit trails receiving the highest grade, indicating that respondents found the system to be very secure when

generating historical records for audit purposes. The vital role of these security measures in risk mitigation and overall corporate system security stresses the relevance of data confidentiality, access control, user authentication, and audit logging techniques (Wang, Xu, & Wang, 2023). The overall weighted mean across all four categories is 4.51, indicating "Very Secure." The system thoroughly analyzed different areas of system security, such as data confidentiality, access control, user authentication, and audit logging procedures.

Conclusions

The development of a municipal emergency response system (MERS) that incorporates GMAPS and SMS can help to improve emergency response times. It aims to prevent the loss of life, property damage, and other negative effects of an emergency, as well as the time it takes to respond to emergencies, by displaying the location of the occurrence on GMAPS and prompting communication via SMS. The new system's characteristics underlined the necessity of strong account verification, multi-channel communication, accurate location data, multimedia proof, and rapid user registration processes in various digital systems and apps. The system evaluation offers promising results in all qualities such as functionality, efficiency, reliability, and security of an emergency response that occurs in the municipality and can be applied as the utility model of emergency response in most municipalities.

Recommendations

The researchers recommend to avail the premium account of Google Maps to have a more accurate and efficient Spot Map of the location to easily verified incident report. It is recommended also to implement the system in the entire barangays of the municipality for better results.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare that there was no conflicts of interest and no bias in the interpretation of the results during and after the implementation of the system, plagiarism was avoided and results were used only for educational purposes.

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